

Multimodal Machine Learning Algorithm as a Tool for Dementia Clinical Trial Screening

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Abstract

Dementia is a complex disease due to various etiologies. However, new multimodal machine learning algorithms were developed to improve the diagnosis of dementia into different categories, including normal cognition (NC), mild cognitive impairment (MCI), Alzheimer's disease (AD), and non-AD dementias (nADD). One of the core difficulties in implementing dementia clinical trials, especially the AD trials lies in the diagnostic ambiguity of Alzheimer's, where symptomatic overlap with other cognitive disorders often leads to misdiagnosis. There are usually high screen failure rates in dementia clinical trials, which is a burden for the sponsor due to the manual verification of the screening that hinders the process. In this study, we aimed to explore the application of a multimodal machine learning algorithm as a tool for clinical trial patients' disease screening verification to reduce the cost of the clinical study by improving its quality, accessibility, and speed. The accuracy assessment of the machine learning algorithm will be presented by comparing its results to a neurologist's evaluation. The results will be described using the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) in a real-world clinical trial setting. We will explore the optimal set of input variables used for the algorithm to balance the medical exams' accuracy, cost, and time.

Key Words: multimodal deep learning algorithm, Dementia clinical trial, disease screening, sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV, real-world

1. Introduction

1.1 Literature Review

Dementia, as defined by the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD), is "a syndrome due to disease of the brain, usually of a chronic or progressive nature, in which there is a disturbance of multiple higher cortical functions, including memory, thinking, orientation, comprehension, calculation, learning capacity, language, and judgment" (World Health Organization, 2019). Dementia is not a specific pathology but rather a syndrome that can be caused by approximately 55 diseases (Geldmacher & Whitehouse, 1996). The most common illnesses that lead to neurodegeneration and dementia are Alzheimer's disease (62%), vascular dementia (17%), mixed dementia (10%), dementia with Lewy bodies (4%), frontotemporal dementia (2%), parkinson's dementia (2%) and other (3%) (Vermeiren et al., 2020). Alzheimer's disease (AD), characterized by the accumulation of amyloid-beta plaques and aggregation of tau

protein tangles in the brain which leads to death of neurons (Scheltens et al., 2021), is the most common cause of dementia which affects 44 million people with an average age of 65 worldwide (Dumurgier 2020; Scheltens et al., 2021; Hendrie, 1998). The number of AD patients is expected to triple by 2050. Thus, it is a major public health concern that has puzzled the most experienced researchers worldwide.

Alzheimer's disease can have an enormous impact on individual patients as well as their loved ones, due to the changes that the disease brings. It also can create a substantial economic burden as there are direct medical and care costs for individuals, families and organizations such as nursing homes. The Alzheimer's disease's indirect consequences, such as loss of productivity, cause high societal costs (Meek, 1998). Despite numerous treatment approaches that have been investigated over the years, there is yet neither curative nor preventive treatment, however there are emerging disease modifying treatments (Passeri et al., 2022). In addition, the escalating prevalence underscores the urgent necessity for further research to understand the nature of AD and discover effective treatments.

The development of effective treatments depends on high quality clinical trials, particularly the accurate selection of patients for enrollment with correct disease diagnosis. The current diagnosis of dementia related to Alzheimer's disease mainly follows the National Institute on Aging and Alzheimer's Association NINCDS-ADRDA criteria. These criteria are mainly based on single modal of neuropsychological tests like the Alzheimer's Disease Assessment Scale-Cognitive (ADAS-Cog), the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE), and the Clinical Dementia Rating scale (CDR) (Balsis et al., 2015).

Alzheimer's disease is often misdiagnosed with other dementias. For example, the differential diagnosis between Alzheimer's disease and vascular dementia remains challenging due to overlaps of symptoms and risk factors (Kalaria, 2002). Moreover, dementia can be a mixed type, combining Alzheimer's disease, vascular dementia, and other dementia disorders (Jellinger, 2007; Alzheimer's Association, 2022).

A new group of biomarkers have been researched in understanding AD progression, leading to improvements of diagnostic accuracy of AD (Budelier & Bateman, 2019; Hurtado et al., 2018; Bai et al., 2021; Chang et al., 2021; Zetterberg & Blennow, 2021; Aeqin et al., 2022; Badhwar et al., 2019; Tan et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2021). Biomarkers for amyloid-beta and tau proteins in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF); and brain imaging techniques such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and positron emission tomography (PET) (Walhovd et al., 2010) were developed. Rapid growth in studies of biofluid and neuroimaging biomarkers for Alzheimer's disease had a tremendous effect on our understanding of disease diagnosis and progression. Furthermore, they led to the release of Revised Criteria for Diagnosis and Staging of Alzheimer's Disease by the National Institute on Aging and Alzheimer's Association (NIA-AA) (Jack et al., 2024). This clinical guidance is a promising tool for improved diagnostic and prognostic accuracy. It also expands our knowledge of AD's biological nature. Nevertheless, there is still a lack of research done towards the understanding of mechanisms and progression of dementia with co-existing pathologies.

With the emergence of technologies, such as AI, and the availability to collect, store, and analyze large amounts of data, researchers started looking for data-driven methodologies for studying the etiology and progression of dementia. AI-based computational models in dementia research have been transformative, enabling the application of multimodal machine-learning (ML) algorithms to improve patients' disease screening accuracy (Wong - Lin et al., 2020). Supervised machine-learning models have been particularly effective in biomarker discovery and neuroimaging studies (Skolariki & Exarchos, 2020). These algorithms combine diverse data types, such as neuroimaging, body fluid biomarkers, and genetic and proteomic data to detect early-stage dementia (Senanarong, 2021; Karako et al., 2023). There are multiple recent studies on using ML for Alzheimer's disease prediction and detection in its early stages based on training their models on the most common data collected particularly for AD (Franciotti et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2024; Alatrany et al., 2024). However, we haven't found any reports on training AI on combined data used for

diagnosis and differentiating different types of dementia. This approach could improve the classification of dementia patients by detecting overlapping mechanisms of co-existing dementia etiologies unseeable to physicians.

1.2 Gap

The challenge of diagnosing Alzheimer's disease accurately is a major limitation in the development of effective treatments. The variety of investigations for AD diagnosis highlights the disease's complex biological heterogeneity. These include advanced imaging methods like MRI and PET scans, detailed neuropsychological evaluations, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis. There is no single test that can definitively diagnose AD.

This diagnostic ambiguity can lead to misdiagnosis, impacting the enrollment accuracy of suitable candidates in clinical studies. Participants with similar symptoms but different underlying etiology can introduce variability in study results. This prevents medical researchers from assessing the true efficacy and safety of potential treatments. Therefore, there is an urgent need for better diagnostic tools that can accurately identify AD. Improved diagnostic methods will improve the clinical trial quality and efficiency by lowering screening costs and refining participant selection.

1.3 Research Question and Project Goal

The objective of this project is to investigate and validate a multimodal prediction model of explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) for the precise classification of possible dementia patients into four distinct categories: normal cognition (NC), mild cognitive impairment (MCI), Alzheimer's disease (AD), and non-Alzheimer's dementias (nADD). Multiple models were investigated to create the optimal combination of multimodal input data to find the balance between diagnostic precision and cost-effectiveness of model input. By validating the model using real world clinical trial data, this study will test the effectiveness of this model in accurately diagnosing dementia participants automatically. This would create the economic benefit of reducing screen failure rates and associated expenses in dementia-related clinical trials. The model's performance will be assessed by comparing model diagnosis and expert evaluations conducted by trained physicians based on the accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) within a real world clinical trial setting.

2. Method

2.1 Justification for chosen method

The primary methodology of this research is based on the multimodal classification prediction model described by (El-Sappagh et al., 2021) supplemented with explainable artificial intelligence (XAI). A random forest (RF) classifier was used for training the model and XAI accompanied each diagnostic decision with a comprehensible rationale, thereby fostering trust and transparency in clinical settings of AI model use.

Previous generations of AI models rely on unimodal data, for example, sourced from either neuroimaging or CSF concentration. Considering the heterogeneous nature of AD, we aimed to build a multimodal model that included a diverse list of clinical assessments and biomarkers.

Moreover, the low explainability of the machine learning models prevents them being used in clinic trials. Hence, XAI was proposed and introduced into AD diagnosis to generate the model's decision explanations. SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) framework was used in the modeling XAI for the random forest classifier's decisions. The framework provides both global and instance-based explanations of the decision assisting the model user with justification of the diagnosis.

The model accuracy and reliability were evaluated using F1-scores in cross-validation settings. The explanations generated from the algorithm were checked with medical literature for consistency.

In this study, the application of El-Sappagh et al.'s model is extended to the realm of clinical trial patient selection. By adapting this model to the clinical trial application, we aimed to reduce the high screen failure rates across dementia trials. Integration of multimodal machine learning and explainable AI could contribute to more efficient and cost-effective patient screening processes, thereby in order to accelerate the development of AD therapeutics.

2.2 Data Collection

The model has been trained and validated using the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) database (adni.loni.usc.edu), which includes a wide spectrum of AD-related cases and healthy controls. We obtained data from 1640 subjects in total from the ADNI dataset.

The model was also tested with a real-world clinical trial study. This data was collected as a part of a real world clinical trial in Alzheimer's disease. Trial data contains 439 subjects who enrolled the study based on AD diagnosis. Inclusion criteria included male and female subjects aged 60 to 85; NINCDS-ADRDA criteria which enables only approximate AD diagnosis (possible or probable Alzheimer's disease) (McKhann et al., 2011); CDR Standard Global score of 1 to 2; MMSE score ≥ 14 and ≤ 24 ; amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) positivity on PET scan; evidence of progressive cognitive decline in last year, etc. During study, different data modalities were collected such as medical history, FDG-PET, MRI, lab tests, neuropsychological assessments, and genetics.

Among the most discriminant and informative 28 features for the modeling, common features were selected: ADAS-Cog 11, MMSE, CDR sum of boxes (CDRSB), gender, and ethnicity. Other available common features were utilized, including Apolipoprotein E (APOE) $\epsilon 4$ genotype, MRI volumes of whole brain, hippocampus, ventricles, and intracranial region.

The model then integrated the selected 10 features with 1640 subjects from ADNI dataset: 462 cognitively normal, 894 mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and 284 AD; as well as the 439 subjects diagnosed as AD from the real world clinical trial data.

2.3 Prediction Models

Random forest, a machine learning algorithm that generates a single result by aggregating the output of several decision trees, is used as the diagnostic algorithm in this research, due to its robust and accurate characteristics among machine learning models. Four experiments are conducted to fully utilize the features and maximize the number of participants: i) using 6 features without model optimization, ii) using 6 features with model optimization, iii) using 10 features without model optimization, and iv) using 10 features with model optimization. The 6-feature experiments were conducted by building RFmodel using APOE $\epsilon 4$ genotype (APOE4), CDR Sum of Boxes (CDRSB), 11-item version of ADAS-Cog (ADAS11), MMSE, gender (PTGENDER), ethnicity (PTETHCAT), while the 10-feature experiments included four more additional features, which are Ventricles, Hippocampus, Whole Brain, intracranial volume (ICV).

In the second part of our study, we built 4 more models by extending a number of features in previously described models. New features, amyloid-beta 42/40 ratio in plasma and CDR Global score, were added to each model from the first part simultaneously resulting in 8- and 12-feature models; or CDR Global score only was added resulting in 7- and 11-feature models.

The models were trained and validated using the ADNI datasets with 5-fold cross-validation. Then, real world clinical dataset was used for testing models' classification predictions. The evaluation metric used in this research is accuracy, which is the percentage of correctly classified instances out of the total instances.

3. Results

3.1 Findings

The analysis shows that across the two datasets, the distribution of features varies greatly, except for the APOE4 allele (as shown in Figure 1). Table 1 details the evaluation metrics of four distinct experiments conducted: i) a random forest detection model utilizing six features without any model optimization, ii) the same random forest model using six features but with grid search optimization, iii) a random forest model utilizing ten features without optimization, and iv) the ten-feature random forest model enhanced with grid search optimization. The findings reveal that applying grid search optimization marginally increases the detection accuracy by 0.1%. Moreover, incorporating additional MRI-derived features boosts the accuracy further by 0.9%. Based on confusion matrices (Figs. 2-5), $PPV = TP / (TP + FP)$ and $NPV = TN / (TN + FN)$ were calculated: i) for 6-feature model without optimization $PPV=64.9\%$ and $NPV=90.5\%$; ii) for 6-feature model with optimization $PPV=66.1\%$ and $NPV=90.8\%$; iii) for 10-feature model without optimization $PPV=65.1\%$ and $NPV=91.9\%$; iv) for 10-feature model with optimization $PPV=65\%$ and $NPV=91.3\%$.

Figure 1: Distributions of the same feature in two datasets

Table 1: Detection accuracy of different experiments

<i>Number of features</i>	<i>Model optimization</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>
6	No	82.5% (2.5%)
6	Yes	82.6% (2.8%)
10	No	83.3% (2.7%)
10	Yes	83.4% (2.9%)

Figure 2: Confusion matrix of the detection results by random forests with 6 features and no optimization

Figure 3: Confusion matrix of the detection results by random forests with 6 features and optimization

Figure 4: Confusion matrix of the detection results by random forests with 10 features and no optimization

Figure 5: Confusion matrix of the detection results by random forests with 10 features and optimization

The 6-feature model without optimization diagnosed only 4.9% of AD patients. All others (95.1%) were misdiagnosed. Despite the minor enhancement from optimization, the prediction accuracy of the 6-feature model displayed considerable difference compared to the same model but without optimization. Optimized model prediction of misdiagnosed patients decreased to 51.7% (as shown in Tables 2 and 3). Conversely, the 10-feature model, regardless of optimization status, consistently predicted misdiagnosis in all cases (as shown in Tables 4 and 5).

Table 2: Prediction results by random forests with 6 features and no optimization

<i>AD</i>	<i>MCI</i>
<i>n predicted (%)</i>	<i>n predicted (%)</i>
10 (4.9%)	203 (95.1%)

Table 3: Prediction results by random forests with 6 features and optimization

<i>AD</i>	<i>MCI</i>
<i>n predicted (%)</i>	<i>n predicted (%)</i>
98 (48.3%)	115 (51.7%)

Table 4: Prediction results by random forests with 10 features and no optimization

<i>AD</i>	<i>MCI</i>
<i>n predicted (%)</i>	<i>n predicted (%)</i>
0	47 (100%)

Table 5: Prediction results by random forests with 10 features and optimization

<i>AD</i>	<i>MCI</i>
<i>n predicted (%)</i>	<i>n predicted (%)</i>
0	47 (100%)

In the second part of the experiment, two more features were added: amyloid-beta 42/40 ratio in plasma and CDR Global score. However, due to a lack of amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) 42/40 ratio data for a significant number of subjects, experiments from the first part were run one more time but with a decreased number of subjects so that importance of added new features (as shown in Table. 6) could be compared.

Table 6: Summary of 12 experiments due to adding $A\beta$ 42/40 ratio and CDR Global. 6 features: APOE ϵ 4 genotype (APOE4), CDR Sum of Boxes (CDRSB), 11-item version of ADAS-Cog (ADAS11), MMSE, gender (PTGENDER), ethnicity (PTETHCAT). 7 features: 6 features + CDR Global. 8 features: 7 features + $A\beta$ 42/40 ratio. 10 features: 6 features + 4 MRI features. 11 features: 7 features + 4 MRI features. 12 features: 8 features + 4 MRI features

n features	n participants in training dataset	n participants in testing dataset	CN	MCI	AD	Optimization	Accuracy	n predicted AD	n predicted MCI
6	1640	446	462	894	284	-	0.79	309	137
6	1640	446	462	894	284	+	0.8	0	446
10	1640	50	462	894	284	-	0.8	0	50
10	1640	50	462	894	284	+	0.8	0	50
7	1640	446	462	894	284	-	0.83	421	25
7	1640	446	462	894	284	+	0.83	44	402
8	283	356	88	187	8	-	0.88	0	356

8	283	356	88	187	8	+	0.89	0	356
11	1640	50	462	894	284	-	0.82	49	1
11	1640	50	462	894	284	+	0.82	0	50
12	283	26	88	187	8	-	0.89	0	26
12	283	26	88	187	8	+	0.89	0	26

Distributions for those 6 models (as shown in Fig. 6 – Fig. 11) have also been compared, which are slightly different as shown in Figure 1, that most likely is caused by the fact that testing real world clinical trial data does not contain CN and MCI.

Figure 6: Distributions of the same features in training (ADNI) and testing real world clinical (Lab Data) for 6-feature model

Figure 7: Distributions of the same features in training (ADNI) and testing real world clinical (Lab Data) for 7-feature model

Figure 8: Distributions of the same features in training (ADNI) and testing real world clinical (Lab Data) for 8-feature model

Figure 9: Distributions of the same features in training (ADNI) and testing real world clinical (Lab Data) for 10-feature model

Figure 10: Distributions of the same features in training (ADNI) and testing real world clinical (Lab Data) for 11-feature model

Figure 11: Distributions of the same features in training (ADNI) and testing real world clinical (Lab Data) for 12-feature model

Some examples of natural-language explanations are provided to understand random forest model decisions which are shown in Tables 7 and 8.

Table 7: Explainer for case-study 1

Subject ID: 113-0013. Diagnosis: MCI

Explanations based on MRI, Medical History, Lab Tests, Symptoms, and Vital Signs modalities

Ventricles

1. Based on MRI dataset:

MCI because Intracranial Volume is **HIGH**, Ventricles is **LOW**, and Hippocampus is **MEDIUM**.

2. Based on Medical History dataset:

MCI because APOE4 is **LOW**, Cardiovascular History is **HIGH**.

3. *Based on Lab Tests dataset:*

MCI because Monocytes is **HIGH**, Cholesterol is **LOW**.

4. *Based on Symptoms dataset:*

MCI because Depression is **NO**.

5. *Based on Vital Signs dataset:*

MCI because Height is **HIGH**, BMI, and Heart Rate are **LOW**, and Temperature is **MEDIUM**.

Table 8: Explainer for case-study 2

Subject ID: 116-0010. Diagnosis: AD

Explanations based on Medical History, Cognitive Scores, Genetics, and Symptoms modalities

1. *Based on Medical History dataset:*

AD because Cardiovascular History is **NO**, APOE4 is **HIGH**, and Psychiatric History are **YES**.

2. *Based on Cognitive Scores dataset:*

AD because CDGLOBAL is **LOW**, and CDRSB is **MEDIUM**.

3. *Based on Genetics dataset:*

AD because ABETA is **POSITIVE** and TAU is **POSITIVE**.

4. *Based on Symptoms dataset:*

AD because Depression is **YES**.

3.1 Quantitative or qualitative

This research employs a quantitative approach. It is based on computational evaluation of numerical data sourced from the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative dataset and clinical study. The data collection included gathering of information on distinct discriminant features like the Alzheimer's Disease Assessment Scale-Cognitive, Mini-Mental State Examination, and Clinical Dementia Rating Sum of Boxes scores, in addition to genetic markers and neuroimaging data. These quantifiable features were utilized for statistical analysis and interpretation.

It is worth noting that not all data were quantitative at the time of collection. Cognitive scores had numerical values initially; brain volume values were obtained after preprocessing neuroimages in FreeSurfer software; demographic data, such as sex and ethnicity, were coded from categorical to numeric values; and genotypic data were initially collected as nucleotide sequences. Knowing the sequence for the APOE4 allele, the number of copies can then be calculated.

Further, preprocessed quantitative data is used to train random forest classifier. The output of predictive model employs a qualitative approach. We applied supervised learning using 3 labels (CN, MCI, and AD) to train our algorithm to categorize patients into 2 categorical groups.

4. Discussion

4.1 Interpretations

The observed inconsistency in feature distribution between the ADNI dataset and the Lab Data (Figure 1) is attributed to the distinct composition of subject groups within each dataset. The ADNI dataset encompasses a wider cognitive range: cognitively normal individuals, those with mild cognitive impairment, and patients diagnosed with Alzheimer's disease, whereas the Lab Data exclusively comprises individuals diagnosed with AD by physicians. This variation naturally explains the shift in distribution, as higher scores in CDRSB and ADAS-Cog11 indicate more severe cognitive impairment, while higher MMSE scores are linked to better cognitive function.

The predictive outcomes from the model, which predominantly classified patients as having MCI rather than AD, warrant a nuanced interpretation. There are 2 possible explanations. Two principal factors may account for this observation.

Firstly, the model's reliance on cognitive scores and genetics as the main predictive features, while MRI modalities did not emerge as significant for the AD class. Cognitive assessments alone, without the support of other investigations, may not possess the specificity required to distinguish AD from other forms of dementia, such as vascular dementia. This is due to the similar symptoms that AD shares with other cognitive disorders, which clinical history and neuropsychological tests alone may not adequately differentiate.

Secondly, ADNI data is labeled in 3 groups: CN, MCI, and AD. However, further subcategorization should have been conducted because MCI can be broadly divided into 2 groups: MCI due to Alzheimer's disease and MCI due to other etiology. This lack of differentiation likely led the model to classify all dementia cases as AD, since only MCI cases with an Alzheimer's cause progress to AD, while MCI cases due to other causes progress to non-Alzheimer's dementias.

These insights highlight the intricate nature of AD diagnosis and the necessity for comprehensive diagnostic strategies. Moreover, they emphasize the importance of strict protocol adherence in clinical research to safeguard the validity and reliability of the outcomes.

The second part with 12 experiments (Tab. 6) underlines the importance of usage of concentrations of plasma A β as well as CDR global scores because accuracy is increased when utilizing both features. However the model that uses 8 features was limited by the low number of subjects. It is necessary to find data from a higher number of subjects to build better predictions. Further, adding grid search optimization to 6-, 7-, and 11-feature models gives different prediction results compared with non-optimized same models although accuracy hasn't changed significantly. This finding leads to the conclusion that my diagnostic AI model does not work correctly, and more work is needed to find out what causes such a major shift in predictions when using optimization.

Natural language-based explanations are necessary for understanding random forest (RF) model decisions. Moreover, these case-study explainers allow us to take a look at a broader picture of patients' profiles. These explainers include assessment results which RF model didn't consider informative and discriminant, however, medical experts prefer individualized explanations for each specific patient according to his/her conditions that cover a wider range of patient data than the RF model, which has been found to be very important.

4.2 Connections

This research has underscored the value of cognitive assessments as dependable markers for forecasting AD. The MMSE, CDRSB, and ADAS-Cog 11 have proven to be vital in the AD diagnosis process. In contrast, data from MRImagnetic resonance imaging (MRI) did not demonstrate remarkable predictive power for AD in my studies. Furthermore, while the apolipoprotein E ϵ 4 allele increases genetic risk for Alzheimer's disease, it is not used in diagnosis.

This highlights the need for additional research to clarify its role and potential utility in identifying the disease.

4.3 Significance

Implementing a multimodal machine learning model in a practical clinical study environment represents a noteworthy advancement in diagnosing neurodegenerative diseases. This research has pinpointed critical features that are essential in accurately classifying Alzheimer's disease. The model's capacity to deliver high prediction accuracy with a relatively small set of biomarkers highlights its effectiveness and potential for real-world application. This study's findings demonstrate several impactful outcomes.

Firstly, the model's dependence on a concise yet effective set of features for AD diagnosis suggests that a more simplified diagnostic process is achievable without sacrificing accuracy. This aspect is particularly valuable in clinical environments where comprehensive testing may be cost-prohibitive or not universally accessible.

Secondly, the encouraging outcomes from the model's application lay the groundwork for its further improvement and adaptation. By incorporating more biomarkers and clinical data, the model's diagnostic precision, in terms of sensitivity and specificity, can be enhanced, leading to more accurate AD detection. Furthermore, the model's cost-efficiency and quick adaptability make a strong argument for its integration into regular clinical workflows, notably in early screening of AD across varied patient groups.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Limitations

Our study has some limitations. Firstly, relying solely on cognitive tests and the APOE ϵ 4 genetic marker doesn't fully capture the complexity needed to differentiate Alzheimer's disease from other types of dementia. In particular, the exclusion of cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers, such as amyloid-beta and tau protein levels, is a major restriction. The inclusion of these markers could significantly improve the accuracy of AD diagnostics. Secondly, the model did not encompass the fourth group of patients who were suspected patients with AD, however, their cognitive impairment was found to have other etiology, such as vascular dementia or Parkinsonism.

5.2 Implications

The outcomes of this study indicate that a multimodality of biomarkers is essential to refine diagnostic precision. Expanding the diagnostic framework to include a wider range of genetic markers, biofluid biomarkers, patient medical history, and neuroimaging data could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the disease. Such an approach is likely to result in enhanced patient care and outcomes.

5.3 Future Research

Future work should be certainly focused on relabeling MCI subjects as not all mild cognitive impairments are caused by AD. It is also necessary to look into each patient's diagnosis throughout the whole study to exclude those who were misdiagnosed at the beginning of ADNI research. Correct categorization of patients is a key to understanding disease progression and building AI models as a diagnostic tool.

Looking ahead, our future research efforts will be directed towards a deeper understanding of AD's main pathophysiological mechanisms, specifically the accumulation of A β plaques and tau protein tangles. The goal is to determine a conversion factor for these proteins from blood plasma samples to CSF, thereby improving the predictive power of my model, and to incorporate patient medical history information to more accurately differentiate AD from vascular dementia. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the model's predictions, it is necessary to consult an AD diagnostic expert

for validation of my approach, thereby affirming the model's utility in diagnosing patients based on study data.

Data availability

Data used in preparation of this article were obtained from the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) database (adni.loni.usc.edu). As such, the investigators within the ADNI contributed to the design and implementation of ADNI and/or provided data but did not participate in analysis or writing of this report. A complete listing of ADNI investigators can be found at: http://adni.loni.usc.edu/wp-content/uploads/how_to_apply/ADNI_Acknowledgement_List.pdf

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References

- Aerqin, Q., Wang, Z. T., Wu, K., He, X., Dong, Q., & Yu, J. (2022, November 8). Omics-based biomarkers discovery for Alzheimer's disease. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00018-022-04614-6>
- Badhwar, A., McFall, G. P., Sapkota, S., Black, S. E., Chertkow, H., Duchesne, S., Masellis, M., Liang, L., Dixon, R. A., & Bellec, P. (2019, December 13). A multiomics approach to heterogeneity in Alzheimer's disease: focused review and roadmap. *Brain*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awz384>
- Bai, B., Vanderwall, D., Li, Y., Wang, X., Suresh, P., Wang, H., Dey, K., Chen, P., Yang, K., & Peng, J. (2021, August 12). Proteomic landscape of Alzheimer's Disease: novel insights into pathogenesis and biomarker discovery. *Molecular Neurodegeneration*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13024-021-00474-z>
- Balsis, S., Bengtson, J. F., Lowe, D. A., Geraci, L., & Doody, R. S. (2015, October 3). How Do Scores on the ADAS-Cog, MMSE, and CDR-SOB Correspond? *The Clinical Neuropsychologist*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13854046.2015.1119312>
- Blennow, K., De Leon, M. J., & Zetterberg, H. (2006, July 1). Alzheimer's disease. *The Lancet*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(06\)69113-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(06)69113-7)
- Budelier, M. M., & Bateman, R. J. (2019, December 30). Biomarkers of Alzheimer Disease. *The Journal of Applied Laboratory Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1373/jalm.2019.030080>

- Chang, C., Lin, C., & Lane, H. Y. (2021, March 9). Machine Learning and Novel Biomarkers for the Diagnosis of Alzheimer's Disease. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22052761>
- [Epidemiology of Alzheimer's disease: latest trends]. (2020, February 1). PubMed.
- El-Sappagh, S., Alonso, J. M., Islam, S. M. R., Sultan, A., & Kwak, K. S. (2021, January 29). A multilayer multimodal detection and prediction model based on explainable artificial intelligence for Alzheimer's disease. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-82098-3>
- Geldmacher, D. S., & Whitehouse, P. J. (1996). Evaluation of Dementia. In *New England Journal of Medicine* (Vol. 335, Issue 5, pp. 330–336). Massachusetts Medical Society. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejm199608013350507>
- Hendrie, H. C. (1998, March 1). Epidemiology of Dementia and Alzheimer's Disease. *The American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00019442-199821001-00002>
- Hurtado, M. O., Köhler, I., & De Lange, E. C. M. (2018, September 1). Next-generation biomarker discovery in Alzheimer's disease using metabolomics – from animal to human studies. *Bioanalysis*. <https://doi.org/10.4155/bio-2018-0135>
- Jellinger, K. A. (2007, January 1). The enigma of mixed dementia. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2006.09.002>
- Alzheimer's Association. (2022). Mixed dementia. https://www.alz.org/media/Documents/alzheimers-dementia-mixed_dementia-ts.pdf
- Kalaria, R. N. (2002, November 1). Similarities between Alzheimer's disease and vascular dementia. *Journal of the Neurological Sciences*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-510x\(02\)00256-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-510x(02)00256-3)
- Karako, K., Song, P., & Yu, C. (2023, February 28). Recent deep learning models for dementia as point-of-care testing: Potential for early detection. *Intractable & Rare Diseases Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5582/irdr.2023.01015>
- McKhann, G. M., Knopman, D. S., Chertkow, H., Hyman, B. T., Jack, C. R., Kawas, C. H., Klunk, W. E., Koroshetz, W. J., Manly, J. J., Mayeux, R., Mohs, R. C., Morris, J. C., Rossor, M. N., Scheltens, P., Carrillo, M. C., Thies, B., Weintraub, S., & Phelps, C. H. (2011, April 22). The diagnosis of dementia due to Alzheimer's disease: Recommendations from the National Institute on Aging - Alzheimer's Association workgroups on diagnostic guidelines for Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2011.03.005>
- Meek, P. D., McKeithan, E. K., & Schumock, G. T. (1998, March 4). Economic Considerations in Alzheimer's Disease. *Pharmacotherapy: The Journal of Human Pharmacology and Drug Therapy*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1875-9114.1998.tb03880.x>
- Passeri, E., Elkhoury, K., Morsink, M., Broersen, K., Linder, M., Tamayol, A., Malaplate, C., Yen, F. T., & Arab - Tehrany, E. (2022, November 12). Alzheimer's Disease: Treatment Strategies and Their Limitations. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms232213954>
- Scheltens, P., De Strooper, B., Kivipelto, M., Holstege, H., Chételat, G., Teunissen, C. E., Cummings, J. L., & Van Der Flier, W. M. (2021, April 1). Alzheimer's disease. *The Lancet*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)32205-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)32205-4)
- Senanarong, V. (2021). Application of Artificial Intelligence-Machine Learning in Dementia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31031/sbb.2021.05.000608>
- Skolariki, K., & Exarchos, T. P. (2020, January 1). Computational Approaches Applied in the Field of Neuroscience. *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-32622-7_17

- Tan, M. S., Cheah, P., Chin, A., Looi, L., & Chang, S. W. (2021, December 1). A review on omics-based biomarkers discovery for Alzheimer's disease from the bioinformatics perspectives: Statistical approach vs machine learning approach. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compbiomed.2021.104947>
- Vermeiren, Y., Van Dam, D., De Vries, M., & De Deyn, P. P. (2020, December 15). *Psychiatric Disorders in Dementia*. Springer eBooks. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-57231-0_9
- Walhovd, K. B., Fjell, A. M., Brewer, J. B., McEvoy, L. K., Fennema-Notestine, C., Hagler, D. J., Jennings, R. G., Karow, D. S., & Dale, A. M. (2010, January 14). Combining MR Imaging, Positron-Emission Tomography, and CSF Biomarkers in the Diagnosis and Prognosis of Alzheimer Disease. *American Journal of Neuroradiology*. <https://doi.org/10.3174/ajnr.a1809>
- Jack, C. R., Andrews, J. S., Beach, T. G., Buracchio, T., Dunn, B., Graf, A., Hansson, O., Ho, C., Jagust, W., McDade, E., Molinuevo, J. L., Okonkwo, O. C., Pani, L., Rafii, M. S., Scheltens, P., Siemers, E., Snyder, H. M., Sperling, R., Teunissen, C. E., & Carrillo, M. C. (2024). Revised criteria for diagnosis and staging of Alzheimer's disease: Alzheimer's Association Workgroup. *Alzheimer S & Dementia*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.13859>
- World Health Organization. (2019). *Dementia*. In *International statistical classification of diseases and related health problems (11th ed.)*. <https://icd.who.int/browse10/2019/en#/F00-F09>
- Zetterberg, H., & Blennow, K. (2021, February 19). Moving fluid biomarkers for Alzheimer's disease from research tools to routine clinical diagnostics. *Molecular Neurodegeneration*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13024-021-00430-x>
- Wong - Lin, K., McClean, P., McCombe, N., Kaur, D., Sánchez-Bornot, J. M., Gillespie, P., Todd, S., Finn, D. P., Joshi, A., Kane, J., & McGuinness, B. (2020, December 1). Shaping a data-driven era in dementia care pathway through computational neurology approaches. *BMC Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-020-01841-1>
- Wong - Lin, K., McClean, P., McCombe, N., Kaur, D., Sánchez-Bornot, J. M., Gillespie, P., Todd, S., Finn, D. P., Joshi, A., Kane, J., & McGuinness, B. (2020, December 1). Shaping a data-driven era in dementia care pathway through computational neurology approaches. *BMC Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-020-01841-1>
- Xie, L., He, B., Varathan, P., Nho, K., Risacher, S. L., Saykin, A. J., Salama, P., & Yan, J. (2021, May 10). Integrative-omics for discovery of network-level disease biomarkers: a case study in Alzheimer's disease. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbab121>